

(1 ml) were added to it with vigorous stirring, and the mixture was then left at room temperature. The resulting crystals were filtered, washed with methanol, dried at room temperature and recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°).

The same procedure was followed to synthesise the other morpholino/piperidino-methyl analogs (Table 1).

6-Chloro-1-morpholino/piperidino-methyl-3-(substituted-benzoylhydrazono)-2-indolinones (5b): It was prepared by the above method using 6-chloro-3-(substituted-benzoylhydrazono)-2-indolinones (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Head of the Chemistry Department for facilities. Thanks are also due to Dr. R. S. Kapil and Prof S. P. Singh for analytical/spectral data.

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Studies on Quinazoline and Mercaptoquinazoline. Preparation and Antibacterial Activity of 2-(2'-Styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4-(aryluroid)-6-chloro-s-triazine and 2-(2'-Mercapto-3'-(4"-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4,6-bis(aryluroid)-s-triazine

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Manuscript received 24 December 1987, revised 3 June 1988, accepted 2 August 1988

QUINAZOLINE derivatives exhibit various physiological activities¹. It was shown that the introduction of SH group inhibits the proteolytic and insecticidal activities². The urea derivatives possess many therapeutic activities³. Several workers have investigated s-triazine nucleus as potential therapeutic agents and fungicides⁴.

In order to synthesise more active compounds, we have synthesised 2-(2'-styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4-(aryluroid)-6-chloro-s-triazine (1)⁵ and

2-[2'-mercapto-3'-(4"-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino]-4,6-bis(aryluroid)-s-triazine (2)⁶ derivatives.

Experimental

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

2-(2'-Styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine: 2-Styryl-6-amino-4-oxoquinazoline (2.63 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone was added in a well-stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone. The reaction mixture was stirred at 0–5° for 2 h maintaining the pH at 7. It was then poured on crushed ice, filtered and the product crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 340°.

General method of preparation of 2-(2'-styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4-(aryluroid)-s-triazine (1): 2-(2'-Styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine (0.01 mol) and arylureas (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone were refluxed at 80–90° for 3 h maintaining the pH at 7. The mixture was then poured on crushed ice, filtered, and the products were crystallised from ethanol, (70–85%), melting points of the compounds, R=phenyl, 235°; o-tolyl, 242°; m-tolyl, 223°; p-tolyl, 205°; o-nitrophenyl, 196°; m-nitrophenyl, 200°; p-nitrophenyl, 238°; o-chlorophenyl, 246°; m-chlorophenyl, 282°; p-chlorophenyl, 296°; ν_{\max} 1 430–1 440 (NH), 1 660–1 670 (CO), 1 020–1 040 (CH=CH) and 800–810 cm^{-1} (C_2N_2).

2-[2'-Mercapto-3'-(4"-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino]-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine: 2-Mercapto-(4'-methylphenyl)-6-amino-4-oxoquinazoline (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone was added to a well-stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone. The reaction mixture was stirred at 0–5° for 2 h maintaining the pH at 7. It was then poured on crushed ice, filtered and crystallised from ethanol, (81%), m.p. 334°.

General method of preparation of 2-[2'-mercapto-3'-(4"-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino]-4,6-bis(aryluroid)-s-triazine: A mixture of 2-[2'-mercapto-3'-(4"-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino]-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine (0.01 mol) and arylureas (0.02 mol) dissolved in acetone was refluxed at 80–90° for 3 h maintaining the pH at 7. The

mixture was then poured on crushed ice, filtered and crystallised from ethanol to yield the products, melting points of compounds, R=phenyl, 280°; *o*-tolyl, 199°; *m*-tolyl, 189°; *p*-tolyl, 210°; *o*-nitrophenyl, 176°; *m*-nitrophenyl, 205°; *p*-nitrophenyl, 217°; *o*-chlorophenyl, 220°; *m*-chlorophenyl, 190°; *p*-chlorophenyl, 200°; ν_{\max} 1 660 (CO), 1 620–1 530 (quinazoline nucleus) and 3 230–3 240 cm^{-1} (NH).

The purified product was screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method using a species of gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*). Testing was carried out in ethanol solution at the concentration of 10 mg ml^{-1} . The same method was adopted for determining *Klebeilla*. The zone of inhibition of both the activities of the test solution was recorded. The maximum zone of inhibition was obtained for *S. aureus*, in case of 2-(2'-styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6-ylamino)-4-(2'-methylphenylureido)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine. In case of *E. coli*, maximum zone of inhibition was recorded for 2-(2'-styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4-(3'-nitrophenylureido)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine, and against *Klebeilla*, maximum zone of inhibition was for 2-(2'-styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4-(4'-methylphenylureido)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine.

For *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *Klebeilla*, 2-[2'-mercapto-3'-(4"-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino]-4,6-bis(4'-nitrophenylureido)-*s*-triazine, 2-[2'-mercapto-3'-(4"-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6-ylamino]-4,6-bis(2'-methylphenylureido)-*s*-triazine, and 2-[2'-mercapto-3'-(4"-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6-ylamino]-4,6-bis(3'-chlorophenylureido)-*s*-triazine were recorded for the maximum zone of inhibition, respectively.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to South Gujarat University for facilities.

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Synthesis of 2-(6'-Methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4-(phenylureido)-6-(arylamino)-*s*-triazine and Study of their Antitubercular and Antibacterial Activity

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Manuscript received 12 April 1988, accepted 2 August 1988

MANY alkaloids with a quinoline nucleus, the best known being quinine, are antimalarials. Various amino, halogeno, urea and thiourea derivatives of hydroxyquinolines possess biological activities¹.

With a view to get more active compounds we have synthesised 2-(6'-methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4-(phenylureido)-6-(arylamino)-*s*-triazine derivatives (1) and their biological activities were evaluated (Table 1). Antitubercular activity was carried out against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₈₇RV, and antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *Klebsiella*.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

2-(6'-Methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine: 6-Methoxy-2-methyl-4-hydroxyquinoline (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone was added in a well-stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at 0–5° at neutral pH. It was then poured on crushed ice, filtered and crystallised from alcohol, (74%), m.p. 160°.

2-(6'-Methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4-(phenylureido)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine: Phenylurea (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone was added slowly to a solution of 2-(6'-methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol) in acetone at 30–40° and the mixture was stirred for 3 h at neutral pH. The reaction mixture was then poured on crushed ice, filtered and crystallised from alcohol, (69%), m.p. 212°.

General method for preparation of 2-(6'-methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4-(phenylureido)-6-(arylamino)-*s*-triazine: A mixture of 2-(4'-methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4-(phenylureido)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol) and various amines (0.01 mol) in dioxane was refluxed at 80–90° for 3 h maintaining neutral pH. The reaction mixture was then poured on crushed ice, filtered and crystallised from ethanol. The physical and antibacterial activity